

Formation Constants of Metal Chelates of *N*-Benzoyl-*o*- and *p*-Tolyhydroxylamines

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The metal ligand stability constants of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) with *N*-benzoyl-*o*-tolyhydroxyl-amine and *N*-benzoyl-*p*-tolyhydroxylamine and the acid dissociation constants of these ligands have been determined in 50% v/v dioxane-water mixture by employing Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique. The titration medium is maintained at a constant ionic strength (0.1M NaClO₄) and at a temperature, 25° ± 0.1°. The order of stability is found to be Cu > Ni > Zn > Co > Mn. The order of IR shift of the carbonyl stretching frequency of the metal complexes have been compared with the order of stability constants.

VERY few metal complexes of chelating agents having
-C-NOH- as electron donor group appear to have
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been potentiometrically investigated. Recently some workers¹⁻⁴ have determined the stability constants of metal chelates with a few ligands having the above reactive functional group. The present work deals with the study of acid dissociation constant of the ligands, *N*-benzoyl-*o*-tolyhydroxylamine (B(o)THA) and *N*-benzoyl-*p*-tolyhydroxylamine (B(p)THA) and stepwise formation constants of manganese (II), cobalt (II), nickel (II), copper (II) and zinc (II) chelates formed by them. The Calvin-Bjerrum^{5,6} potentiometric titration technique has been used to evaluate the stability constants for the reactions of the metal ions and the ligands in 50% v/v dioxane-water medium at 0.1M NaClO₄ and 25° ± 0.1°. IR spectrum of the metal chelates of B(o)THA have been taken to compare the order of the shift of the carbonyl stretching frequency of the metal chelates with the stability order. The results have been interpreted in terms of factors which has bearing on the stabilities of metal chelates.

Experimental

Material: Dioxane (AnalaR, BDH) was further purified by the method described by Weisseberger⁷ and stored out of contact with air. Approximate 0.2M carbonate free sodium hydroxide was prepared and standardized with analytical grade potassium hydrogen phthalate. It was diluted to give 0.1M solution. The stock solution of sodium perchlorate (neutral) and perchloric acid was prepared by dissolving AnalaR sample of NaClO₄·H₂O (Riedel) and HClO₄ (E. Merk). The concentration of perchloric acid was determined against standard sodium hydroxide. Solutions of perchlorates of manganese (II), cobalt (II), nickel (II), copper (II) and zinc (II) were obtained by dissolving their perchlorate (Fluka) in known quantities of perchloric acid. The metal content in each solution was determined by standard methods⁸ and diluted to give 0.02M solutions. The reagents B(o)THA and B(p)THA were prepared as

described earlier⁹. A weighed amounts of the reagents were directly taken in the dried clean titrating vessel for making solution whenever required for study. Redistilled water was used in all cases.

Apparatus: All pH measurements were made with a Cambridge bench type pH meter equipped with a glass-saturated calomel electrode pair and standardized with buffer solutions at pH 4.00 and 9.00. The design of the glass jacketted cell was such that it allowed nitrogen (presaturated with solvent) to be passed through the titrating mixture and enabled measurements to be carried in an atmosphere of nitrogen. A electrically maintained thermostat and a magnetic stirrer were employed for maintaining constant temperature and stirring of the reacting mixture, respectively.

The infrared spectra were recorded with a Perkin Elmer Infracord spectrophotometer (137). For sample preparation pellet technique was employed using potassium bromide as the matrix material.

The Calvin-Bjerrum titration: The experimental procedure involved potentiometric titration of the ligands with standard (0.1M) alkali in the absence of, and in the presence of, the metal ions to be studied. These included titrations of (a) HClO₄ (5.0 × 10⁻⁴ moles) + reagent (2.0 × 10⁻⁴ moles) and (b) HClO₄ (5.0 × 10⁻⁴ moles) + reagent (2.0 × 10⁻⁴ moles) + metal ion (2.0 × 10⁻⁵ moles). The ionic strength was maintained constant at 0.1M by addition of sodium perchlorate solution. The initial volume of the titration solution was 100 ml aqueous-dioxane containing 50% dioxane by volume. Reaction solutions were, all thermostated at 25° ± 0.1°. The pH meter readings obtained after each equilibrium point at a given alkali addition in duplicate titrations were reproducible with a maximum variation of ± 0.02 pH unit. Necessary pH correction¹⁰ was made for using 50% v/v dioxane-water mixture.

Calculations

Acid dissociation constants: The reagents, B(o)THA and B(p)THA containing each one weakly acidic hydroxyl group was represented as HR. The acid dissociation constant, K_{OH} was calculated from the experimental points in the buffer region using the equation,

$$K_{OH} = \frac{[H^+][S]}{[TR] - [S]}$$

where, $[S] = [H^+] + [Na^+] - [OH^-] - [A]$, $[TR]$ and $[A]$ were the total reagent and perchloric acid concentrations, respectively.

Chelate formation constants: Calvin-Bjerrum method was utilised for calculating chelate formation constants from the following equations,

$$\bar{n} = \frac{1}{[T_M]} \left[[TR] - [S_1] \frac{K_{OH} + [H^+]}{[H^+]} \right]$$

$$R^- = \frac{K_{OH} [S_1]}{[H^+]}$$

where, $[S_1] = [TR] + [A] + [OH^-] - [Na^+] - [H^+]$,

$[T_M]$, \bar{n} and R^- represented total metal ion concentration, average number of chelating agent bound to one metal ion and anionic chelating agent concentration, respectively. The stepwise chelate formation constants $\log K_1$, $\log K_{av}$ and $\log K_2$ were obtained from the plot of \bar{n} against pR^- ($pR^- = -\log R^-$) at values $\bar{n} = 0.5, 1.0$ and 1.5 , respectively.

Results and Discussion

The value of \bar{n} obtained in Cu (II), Ni (II), Co (II), Mn (II) and Zn (II) system was above 1.6 before the onset of precipitation with B(o)THA and B(p)THA. This indicated the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes in solution and clearly ruled out the possibility of the hydrolysis of these metal ions in the presence of a large excess of the reagents. The stoichiometry of the metal chelates formed was evaluated from the potentiometric titration data in the following manner.

In any titration, 0.5 millimole of base was required to neutralise the excess perchloric acid and any protonated species which might be present; consequently, the displacement of the reagent, perchloric acid, and metal ion curve at 0.5 millimole of base from the reagent and perchloric acid was due to proton release, which in turn was dependent on the reaction between reagent and metal ion. The presence of 0.02 millimole of metal ions required 0.04 millimole more of standard sodium hydroxide to reach the neutralisation point. This implied that two equivalents of hydrogen ions had been released per mole of metal ion in solution.

The values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_{av}$ and $\log K_2$ for Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Mn(II) and Zn(II) chelates of B(o)THA Fig. 1 and B(p)THA were directly read from the formation curves. These values were also obtained by the method of least squares¹¹ and are shown within bracket in the Table 1. The \bar{n} versus pR^- curves did not appear to show distinct stepwise addition. This was probably true, since the difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ was not large. Therefore, the ring system of B(o)THA or B(p)THA was such that the tendency for chelate

formation to occur by the stepwise addition of the ligand molecules was diminished, thereby increasing the possibility of simultaneously adding two reagent molecules to a metal ion.

Fig. 1. Formation Curves for binding N-B(O)THA by metal ions.

TABLE 1—METAL CHELATE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF B(O)THA AND B(P)THA

Metal	$\mu = 0.1M (NaClO_4)$			$t = 25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$		
	Metal Chelate of B(o)THA			Metal Chelate of B(p)THA		
	$\log K_1$	$\log K_{av}$	$\log K_2$	$\log K_1$	$\log K_{av}$	$\log K_2$
Copper	9.35 (9.34)	8.52 (8.53)	7.69 (7.72)	9.57 (9.53)	8.63 (8.60)	7.69 (7.70)
Nickel	7.22 (7.17)	6.43 (6.47)	5.71 (5.78)	7.27 (7.25)	6.46 (6.43)	5.77 (5.62)
Cobalt	6.61 (6.58)	6.08 (6.14)	5.64 (5.70)	6.64 (6.63)	6.12 (6.17)	5.68 (5.71)
Manganese	5.51 (5.40)	5.07 (5.13)	4.74 (4.86)	5.57 (5.47)	5.08 (5.18)	4.75 (4.89)
Zinc	6.74 (6.64)	6.05 (6.12)	5.49 (5.60)	6.70 (6.62)	6.04 (6.03)	5.43 (5.44)

The pK_a values of the reagents, B(o)THA and B(p)THA were found to be 10.09 and 10.17 respectively. The slight decrease of pK_a value in the former case was due to the following reasons. Methyl group has +I effect (electron pushing) in either case, but its presence in ortho-compound close to the ionisation site may influence the ionisation by steric interaction¹². With this decrease in pK_a value of B(o)THA, the stability of its metal chelates also correspondingly decreased. The order of stability with respect to $\log K_1$ or $\log \beta_2$ was $Cu > Ni > Zn > Co > Mn$. The position of zinc in this series was anomalous with respect to the stability sequence of Mellor and Maley¹³. On the other hand, the above stability order was the same as for other five membered ring formers with oxygen-nitrogen and oxygen-oxygen donors¹⁴⁻¹⁷.

An approximate parallelism between $\log K_n$ and second ionisation potential was noted (Fig. omitted). The correlation between stability constants with atomic numbers was all the same that was observed previously¹⁸.

The infrared spectra of *N*-benzoyl-*o*-tolylhydroxyl-amine along with its metal chelates were taken¹⁹ to compare the order of the stability constants with the order of the shifts of carbonyl stretching frequencies of the metal chelates. The strong absorption band at 1628 cm⁻¹ in the reagent spectrum was attributed to C=O vibration in the reagent molecule although the observed frequency was much lower than actual due to strong hydrogen bonding. On complex formation with metal ions, this frequency shifted; the Cu (II) chelate showing the largest shift, Mn(II) chelate showed a marked shift and Ni (II), Co (II) and Zn(II) chelates showed shift to the more or less same extent. The interaction of the C=O group with the π bonds in the chelate ring as well as the influence of *d*-electrons of the metal atoms played a much more important part in determining the extent of shifts that were observed in the C=O group vibrations as one passed from the reagent to the metal chelates. The carbonyl stretching frequencies in the Cu (II), Ni (II), Co (II), Mn (II) and Zn (II) complexes had been observed at 1526, 1542, 1548, 1540 and 1546 cm⁻¹ respectively. This showed that for these metal chelate compounds of B(o)THA the order of carbonyl shifts follow the order Cu > Mn > Ni > Zn > Co which agreed generally with the stability order, excepting the inclusion of manganese.

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